

Electrical and Electronics Engineering: An International Journal (ELELIJ)

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Scope & Topics

Electrical and Electronics Engineering: An International Journal (ELELIJ) is a Quarterly peer-reviewed and refereed open access journal that publishes articles which contribute new results in all areas of the Electrical and Electronics Engineering. The journal is devoted to the publication of high quality papers on theoretical and practical aspects of Electrical and Electronics Engineering.

The goal of this journal is to bring together researchers and practitioners from academia and industry to focus on Electrical and Electronics Engineering advancements, and establishing new collaborations in these areas. Original research papers, state-of-the-art reviews are invited for publication in all areas of Electrical and Electronics Engineering.

Topics of interest include but are not limited to, the following

Authors are solicited to contribute to the conference by submitting articles that illustrate research results, projects, surveying works and industrial experiences that describe significant advances in the following areas, but are not limited to

- Advanced Power System and Control system
- Analog and digital circuit design
- Bio Informatics
- Biomedical Instrumentation
- Digital signal processing
- Embedded Systems and Robotics
- Information systems and network security
- Mechatronics and Avionics
- Non Conventional Energy Resources
- Optical Networks & communication
- Optimization techniques
- Power Electronics & Electric Drives
- Remote sensing and satellite communication
- RF and Microwave Engineering
- Semiconductor Devices
- Sensor technology & Virtual Instrumentation
- Soft computing / Nano computing / Grid computing
- System Modeling & Simulation
- VLSI technology & Design

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through the **Submission System**. Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : October 10, 2020**
- Notification : November 10, 2020
- Final Manuscript Due : November 18, 2020
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief